

A NUMERICAL MODEL TO STUDY THE RAPID BUFFERING APPROXIMATION NEAR AN OPEN Ca^{2+} CHANNEL FOR AN UNSTEADY STATE CASE

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Abstract : Chemical reaction and diffusion are important phenomena in quantitative neurobiology and biophysics. The knowledge of the dynamics of calcium Ca^{2+} is very important in cellular physiology because Ca^{2+} binds to many proteins and regulates their activity and interactions. Calcium waves propagate inside cells due to a regenerative mechanism known as calcium-induced calcium release. Buffer-mediated calcium diffusion in the cytosol plays a crucial role in the process. A mathematical model has been developed for calcium waves by assuming the buffers are in equilibrium with calcium i.e., the rapid buffering approximation for a one dimensional unsteady state case. This model incorporates important physical and physiological parameters like dissociation rate, diffusion rate, total buffer concentration and influx. The finite difference method has been employed to predict $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ and buffer concentration time course regardless of the calcium influx. The comparative studies of the effect of the rapid buffered diffusion and kinetic parameters of the model on the concentration time course have been performed.

Keywords : Calcium Concentration Profile, Calcium Influx, dissociation Constant, Buffers.

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